

Physicochemical and antimicrobial studies of some metal complexes

Kamel A. El-Manakhly^{a*}, Hoda A. Bayoumi^b, M. M. Ezz Eldin^c and Hamdy A. Hammad^a

^aChemistry and ^cMicrobiology of Plant Departments, Faculty of Science, Al-Azhar University, Nasr City, Cairo 11884, Egypt

^bChemistry Department, College of Girls, Ain Shams University, Cairo, Egypt

Manuscript received 16 February 1998, accepted 22 July 1998

Some antimicrobial-active metal (Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}) complexes of benzylidene acetylhydrazine (BAH), chlorobenzylidene acetylhydrazine (CBAH) and salicylidene acetylhydrazine (SAH) have been prepared. These complexes are cationic octahedral. The ligands and their complexes show antimicrobial activities and higher antifungal activity (especially Zn^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes) even at low concentration.

Acid hydrazides and hydrazones are interesting chelating agents^{1,2}. Hydrazone derivatives are used as antifungicides and in the treatment of diseases such as tuberculosis, leprosy and mental disorders³.

The aim of the present work was to synthesise complexes of Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with some hydrazones, and evaluate their biological activities.

Results and Discussion

The breaks in the conductometric titration curves (Fig. 1) indicate 1 : 1 and 2 : 1 ligand-metal complexes. The electronic spectra of the copper complexes reveal broad bands due to Jahn-Teller effect centered at 12820, 12500 and 13793 cm^{-1} for BAH, CBAH and SAH complexes respectively, which can be assigned to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$. This indicates that these complexes possess octahedral structure⁴. The differences of the energy of these bands are in good agreement related to ligand field effect of the complexes. The magnetic susceptibilities of the copper complexes of BAH, CBAH and SAH are 1.94, 1.93, and 1.95 B.M.

The main IR bands of the ligands and their complexes are listed in Table 1. The ν_{OH} , ν_{NH} and $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ ligand bands⁵ indicate that these ligands are mixtures of keto and enol forms. On the other hand, a remarkable shift was observed in the above bands upon complexation. It is worth noting that on complexation the intensity of carbonyl band decreases or disappears. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ ligand CBAH band disappeared in the Zn^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes. This implies that these complexes are predominantly present as enol form, while other complexes exist in keto and enol forms. Thermal measurement indicates loss of three molecule of water at 180, 170, 175 and 170° of the Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes with SAH ligand.

Antimicrobial and antifungal activities : The free ligands and their metal complexes exhibited significant inhibitory effect against Gram negative bacteria, and much enhanced effect against Gram positive bacteria, especially the Hg and Cu complexes of SAH, CBAH and BAH at all concentrations (250–2000 ppm). All the Cd and Cu com-

plexes of the ligands showed lower inhibitory effect. Similar results have been reported by other investigators⁶. Complete inhibition of growth was observed after turbidimetrically measurement for 24 h for Eubacteria at 50 ppm Cd for *Bacillus megaterium*, at 100 ppm Cd for caryne bacterium Sp., and at 500 ppm Cd for enterobacter aerogenes and *Bacillus cereus*. The Gram negative bacteria were more tolerant to Cd than the Gram positive. In general, the activity of free ligand and CHAH-complexes against both types of bacteria was found superior but the

Fig. 1. Conductograms of (a) CBAH, (b) SAH and (c) BAH with metal ions.

Table 1. Ir bands of the hydrazones and their complexes

Assignment	BAH	BAH-Cu ^{II}	BAH-Zn ^{II}	BAH-Cd ^{II}	BAH-Hg ^{II}
VOH+VNH	3267 3193	3190	3188	3193	3255
VC=O	1653	1608	1607	1608	1611
VC=N	1608	1574	1574	1525	1538
δOH	1399	1343	1343	1342	1369
VC-O	1137	1137	1336	1137	1136
v ₃ SO ₄ ²⁻	-	1070	-	1071	-
v ₁ SO ₄ ²⁻	-	1021	-	1022	-
ρ _w H ₂ O	-	851	851	850	850
v ₄ SO ₄ ²⁻	-	602	-	603	-
VM-O	-	427	426	428	434
VM-N	-	264	232	321	320
	CBAH	CBAH-Cu ^{II}	CBAH-Zn ^{II}	CBAH-Cd ^{II}	CBAH-Hg ^{II}
VOH+VNH	3187	3189 3073	3225 3091	3225 3089	3224 3088
VC=O	1678	1617	-	1616	-
VC=N	1598	1599	1597	1596	1596
δOH	1397	1355	1336	1335	1332
VC-O	1152	1220	1152	1151	1133
v ₃ SO ₄ ²⁻	-	1048	-	1047	-
v ₁ SO ₄ ²⁻	-	1630	-	1031	-
ρ _w H ₂ O	-	859	858	856	855
v ₄ SO ₄ ²⁻	-	610	-	598	-
VM-O	-	464	464	456	454
VM-N	-	409	394	392	390
	SAH	SAH-Cu ^{II}	SAH-Zn ^{II}	SAH-Cd ^{II}	SAH-Hg ^{II}
VOH+VNH	3188 3077	3401 2963	3309	3190 3079	3432 3077
VC=O	1677	1622	1643	1622	1612
VC=N	1611	1607	1620	1577	1574
δOH	1391	1385	1390	1341	1340
VC-O	1154	1150	1140	1152	1150
v ₃ SO ₄ ²⁻	-	1040	-	1049	-
v ₁ SO ₄ ²⁻	-	1006	-	1031	-
ρ _w H ₂ O	-	883	856	856	855
v ₄ SO ₄ ²⁻	-	603	-	611	-
VM-O	-	469	464	468	454
VM-N	-	324	323	423	422

Gram positive was found resistant and responded lower than the Gram negative.

Antifungal activity of the free ligands and their metal complexes was determined against *Candida albicans*. It has been recognized that the unicellular fungi and the dermatophytes are inhibited by different concentrations of the free ligands and the copper complexes. It is reported⁷ that the copper complexes and all ligands had MIC value as 500 µg ml⁻¹ against *C. utilis*, while in this study, the MIC for *C. albicans* was found sensitive to all the free ligands and their metal complexes when they are grouped according to their MIC values : (a) those inhibited with MIC <50 µg ml⁻¹ like SAH, CBAH and BAH-Zn and BAH-Hg, especially the antidermatophytes activity against species exhibited good response upto <50 µg ml⁻¹ and (b) those in-

hibited with 100–200 µg ml⁻¹ like SAH and CBAH-Cd, CBAH-Cu. The results reveal that the heavy metal complexes improve the antimicrobial activity.

Experimental

All chemicals were of pure grade (Merck, and B.D.H.). Acetic acid hydrazide was prepared^{2,7} by refluxing equimolecular amount of ethyl acetate and hydrazine. The product was condensed with benzaldehyde, salicylaldehyde and 2-chlorobenzaldehyde to give the required hydrazones.

The metal complexes were prepared by refluxing aqueous ethanolic solution of the ligand and CuSO₄, CdSO₄, ZnCl₂ or HgCl₂ in the ratio 1 : 1 for 2 h. On cooling, the complexes that precipitated out were washed with ethanol, ether, and dried under reduced pressure.

All the complexes gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 598 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Perkin-Elmer- Lambda 4B spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility was obtained using Gouy method. Thermal measurement was carried out using a Shimadzu 50 analyzer.

Stoichiometric ratio of the complexes was determined by conductometric titration using a digital conductivity meter (Cale Parmer Instrument Co). Ligands and the metal cations were dissolved in ethanol (0.01 M) and distilled-water (0.001 M) respectively. Each ligand solution was titrated against metal solutions as described previously⁸.

Biological activity : *In vitro* antimicrobial activity of the ligands and complexes was evaluated by using the diffusion method⁹ at concentrations 250, 500, 1000 and 2000 ppm against *Bacillus subtilis* NCTC 8236, *Staphylococcus aureus* NCTC (7447) and *Escherichia coli* BPP01.

References

1. K. A. El-Manakhly, A. A. Shabana and H. A. Hammad, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 715; B. K. Mohapatra, S. Guru and C. D. Rao, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1980, **42**, 1195; N. Saha and S. Sinha, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 203; M. Saha, J. J. Nevada and A. G. Mansilla, *Talanta*, 1981, **28**, 134; A. A. Shabana, K. A. El-Manakhly and H. A. Hammad, *Can. J. Appl. Spectrosc.*, 1994, **39**, 151.
2. M. A. Khaled, H. A. Hammad, A. M. Abdalla and K. A. El-Manakhly, *Can. J. Appl. Spectrosc.*, 1995, **40**, 71.
3. M. Katyal and Y. Dutta, *Talanta*, 1975, **22**, 151.
4. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
5. L. J. Bellamy, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Chapman & Hall, London, 1975; K. Nakamoto, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1970.
6. L. M. Zibilske and G. H. Wagner, *Soil Sci.*, 1982, **134**, 364.
7. Th. Curtius, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1910, **81**, 543.
8. M. G. Abd El-Wahed, K. A. El-Manakhly, S. M. Metwally, H. A. Hammad and S. A. Aly, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1995, **126**, 663.
9. V. Lorian, "Antibiotics in Laboratory Medicine", Baltimore, 1986.